

ONLINE APPLICATION FOR PARKING SLOT REGISTRATION

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Abstract— : Here's an abstract for an online parking slot booking system that includes payment integration with popular services like Google pay , Phone pe, Paytm, Credit card and Debit card. Additionally, the system will generate a barcode that displays the booked parking slot. The system will be built using Python and will consist of two main components: a backend server and a frontend web application. The backend server will handle all the logic related to parking slot booking, payment processing, and barcode generation. It will use a database to store information about available parking slots, bookings, and payment transactions. Here mathematical equations and logical functions are used. The frontend web application will allow users to browse available parking slots and make bookings. The application will display real-time information about available parking slots and update the status of the slots as they are booked. Users will be able to select their preferred payment method and make payments securely using their preferred service. Upon successful payment, the system will generate a barcode that displays the booked parking slot, which users can scan to gain access to the parking lot. In conclusion, this online parking slot booking system will provide users with a convenient and secure way to book parking slot. The application boasts an intuitive and user-friendly interface, allowing users to easily locate, reserve, and manage parking slots with just a few taps on their mobile devices. Real-Time Availability Updates: This feature minimizes the time spent searching for parking spaces and enhances overall user satisfaction. Users can choose from a range of booking options, including hourly, daily, and monthly reservations. Users receive timely reminders for upcoming reservations, ensuring a smooth and punctual parking experience.

Keywords—smart parking system, parking application, parking reservation, slot booking

I. INTRODUCTION

The parking place is very important all over the world especially in the cities of the countries. Every day thousands of car drivers spend a lot of the time to find where to park. The result of this situation is theft in urban areas, increasing traffic congestion and frustration of drivers. In order to solve this problem, the implementation of Online Vehicle Parking System in this city For managing parking places is mandatory. It will allow the drivers to Reserve a parking place on the Platform of People's Park Chennai (PPC) anytime, anywhere. this chapter gives an overview of the background of the study, statement of the problems, Objectives of the study, research questions, scope of the study and significance of the study. People's Park Chennai is located in Chennai district along Shollinganallur –OM Road . It's located 1 mile from Accenture round about, People's Park Chennai Is constructed on 1 Acre of land (measurements 100ft-100ft) in Chennai, it provides Enough space for its well-wishing customers, It is equipped with high maximum security coupled With an electric fence , four gun men from a well training security company and well trained bull Dogs have been also used to control trespassing within the People's Park and with this maximum Security, expenses like compensation of customers' lost vehicles are brought down. The parking place is very important all over the world especially in the cities of the countries.

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II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Licensed Under Creative Commons Attribution CC BY Online Parking System - The paper discusses the problem of traffic congestion caused by increasing numbers of vehicles and the burning of oil due to the search for parking spaces. - It highlights the need to modify materials used for personal and commercial purposes and introduces a new smart parking system that is more economical and eco-friendlier. - The paper presents the working performance and implementation of the smart parking system, as well as the analysis of its reliability. Different modules are implemented in the parking management app, including a user interface module, communication module, function module, and parking space controller module. - The smart parking technology is considered a key solution to parking space problems, long queues, and other parking issues in urban areas.

Remotely booking slot for vehicle using Internet of Things - The paper proposes a system that utilizes IoT and cloud-based technology to provide smart car parking facilities in smart cities. - The system uses RFID technology and suitable IoT protocols to minimize human interference and reduce costs. - A Raspberry Pi is used as a mini-computer in the system, along with a suitable path methodology to calculate the shortest distance between the user and available parking spaces, reducing the users waiting time. - The system also includes the practice of remotely booking a parking slot through an Android application, providing a hassle-free and instantaneous parking experience for car drivers. - The proposed system aims to decrease the average waiting time for parking, reduce the number of cars struggling to find parking spaces, and save users time, money, and reduce pollution.

On-Street Parking Reservation and Toll Management System – The proposed project is a smart on-road parking management system that allows users to book parking spots alongside roads, overcoming the problem of unavailability of parking in commercial areas. - The system provides a web-based reservation system where users can view available parking

spaces and book slots. - After booking a slot, the customer receives two OTPs to their registered email address, which are validated at the gate for entry and exit. - The system efficiently detects empty parking slots and updates the information on the webpage.

Online Car Parking Management System OCPMS - Synopsis of the Paper The issue of obtaining unoccupied parking spaces in congested regions and the challenges experienced by drivers in finding parking places are discussed in the article. – The suggested remedy is an online parking reservation system that enables customers to see several parking lots and book a spot in advance, preventing last-minute difficulty. - Users can access real-time parking information, protection, and guidance through the system. - With the help of the smart parking system, traffic congestion and the inadequacy of the current transportation and parking infrastructure to accommodate the growing number of vehicles would be addressed.

Parking Smart System - The study suggests a smart parking system to alleviate the difficulties with parking cars in metro areas caused by the increasing density of people and vehicles. - The method makes use of a mobile application for operators to identify users and charge them while enabling them to find and reserve parking spaces. - Through the Android app, users may reserve parking spaces using either online or offline payment methods. Additionally, they have the option to revoke reserved timeslots, with a refund of the money less cancellation fees. - The suggested approach intends to reduce users' time by making it simple to locate and reserve parking spaces while also assisting parking owners in keeping track of available spaces.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system structure has altogether the infrared radar nodes which intellects the rank of the vehicle gap besides transference of the facts to the AVR controller and it demonstrates the facts on the led display intended for the customer.

Disadvantages:

- Once the system is corrupted all the images will be lost.
- Security and privacy issues.
- Cost of maintenance.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The system offers a seamless solution for users to efficiently manage their parking needs. Through the platform, users can register for parking slots, select their desired location, date, and time, and securely book their slots. Upon successful booking, users receive a unique QR code, serving as their parking permit. Administrators have access to a comprehensive dashboard for managing parking facilities, including real-time updates on slot availability and revenue generation analytics. The system integrates with exit gates equipped with QR code scanners, allowing users to validate their parking permits and exit smoothly. With features like real-time updates, secure payment integration, and user-friendly interface, our application enhances convenience, efficiency, and security in the parking management process, catering to the needs of both users and administrators alike.

Fig 4.1. System Architecture

The proposed system can also be used in public places for public parking like in malls, station, and so on. In the existing system the parking management were all made in Manual mode, so it's unable to make the process easy and smooth. The project can be implemented in commercial areas for employee parking. It can be utilized by companies and organizations (hospitals, schools, colleges) to automate their parking system. We can implement the online slot to booking areas.

Major problem arising in developed countries is the parking system due to the development of technologies the production of cars where increased. Due to the increment in production of cars, the usage of cars becomes increasing day by day. To reduce the traffic during car parking, we proposed this system. Pi camera is used to continuously monitor the status of the car parking Zone. It updates the presence and absence of cars in a parking Zone. Python image processing techniques have been used to extract the features of presence and absence of car. Haar like features are used for extracting the features of car to identify the presence and absence of car. Raspberry pi3 microcontroller is used for controlling this system. Pi camera continuously updates the status of the parking zone i.e. the availability of places in the parking area. From the information given by the pi camera , microcontroller updates the information to the LED display that are present outside the car parking area and also the status is continuously updated to the web server. This system helps to reduce the traffic in the parking area. This system also saves the time for the customers.

V. MODULE DESCRIPTION:

User login:

Users have to first register themselves to login into the system. In the registration of user page should be filled with the details of Name, Data of Birth, Email ID, Gender, Phone Number, Address and Password. After clicking sign up, the user registration will be made successful. With the details of registration made, the user login should be done. Checking the authorization, the user will be logged in to the system. After logging it, the user can able to see the Parking Cost, Book Parking, Your Booking details.

Admin Login:

The system is under supervision of admin who manages the bookings made. Once after the admin logged it, the admin can see the parking cost, View User details and View Bookings. Only the admin has the privilege of modifying the parking cost. Also admin can view the user details. And also the admin can view the complete booking details with the cost etc.

Parking availability:

User can click on spaces to view the availability. If the space is already booked it will be marked yellow and the available ones will be seen in normal color. Parking booking online for date and time: Users can book parking space for their required date and time. User cannot select the slot if the booking is already done by some other earlier.

Automatic cost calculation:

The system calculates the total cost incurred for parking based on the time that user has asked for booking. In the user login, the option: Book Parking is available. In this the user enters the details of Date, time, and parking hours. After entering the details, the hours are calculated automatically and the final amount is displayed. The user no needs to calculate the amount and enter it manually connection. It requires large database. It take overtime to spend for shopping.

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS

As a result of its powerful sensor-based detection that makes use of wireless sensor networks (WSNs), the suggested system outperforms the current one in terms of efficiency.

Fig 5.1. Ticket Booking

After booking the tickets, the respective car parking zone will be reserved for the particular time period.

Fig 5.2. CAR weight space

The fig5.2 shows the parking area being monitored by the System The space and height the car. whenever the new car enters and leaves the parking area.

A combination of automation and data-driven analysis, offers increased accuracy and more dependable explosive substance identification. Furthermore, because of its flexibility, scalability, and quick reaction time, it can effectively handle a wide range of security requirements in a variety of settings. The suggested solution enables constant monitoring and reduces false alarms by utilizing machine learning and data analytics, which improves overall operational efficiency. Its strong data security measures and smooth integration with cutting-edge technology further establish its superiority over the old system's restricted capabilities, giving it a more effective way to identify and counteract explosive threats.

VII. CONCLUSION

Online vehicle parking reservation system improves the existing system since we are in Computerized world. With this new system is mandatory, it enables the user of the system (client ,Employee, System administrator) to reserve a parking lot online and this reduces the wasting of Time of the clients looking for where to park, increase the safety of the property since the parking lot is numbering. The difficulty of searching available parking lots has been completely eliminated by receiving lots via the proposed system. User can get learn about parking areas for particular location. It saves user time in search of parking space available in such long parking area. In the further development of this Android app plan to make the app more advance by adding more support and additional functions to the system .Also plan to use credit card payment gateway instead of G pay and Paytm.

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